

THE PLACE OF ART IN THE FOLK GAMES

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Abstract: This article has developed over centuries in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, and puppetry has become one of the people's favorite and most enjoyable shows with its creative activity as a popular performance art from the earliest times.

Key words: "Tent dream", "Chadir Jamal", "Lantern dream", games, folklore, ethnography, mumtaz.

INTRODUCTION

Puppetry, which has been developing for centuries in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, has become one of the people's favorite and most enjoyable shows with its creative activity as a popular performance art from the earliest times. "For this reason, we must preserve and develop classic art, rare examples of folk creativity, which is our incomparable spiritual wealth, and pass it on to future generations..." [1, B. 135] is our corner.

The art of puppetry, like other types of folk art, is folk has reached today based on the teacher-disciple tradition, as well as oral creativity. This art form, with its performances, has been gathering events and events, negative evils that are happening in the process of the social system of its time through stage works. In Uzbekistan, the folk art of puppetry has developed in the past, and its types "Imagination Tent", "Chadir Jamal", "Fonus Imagination" have been performing. The representatives of the old puppetry art say that the organization of the puppet show required a lot of hard and enduring work. Because there were no ready-made texts in this art either.

The topics of the show are determined according to the audience's taste and taste, and the doll is chosen according to the show.

The characters of the people who lived at that time are reflected through the ancient puppetry, including "Chadir Jamal", "Chadir Myam", "Fonus Myam" folk performances.

Chodir jamal is a type of traditional Uzbek puppetry. In it puppets are played with hands. Accordingly, he is called a "hand puppet" is conducted. His shows are mostly shown during the day. The stage is often made of red or yellow hard gauze and is called a tent. The puppeteer enters the tent and ties the lower part around his waist, and the upper part over his head takes the shape of a square

stage with the help of a lover's pole, a threshold, two side poles and pegs. The puppeteer, crouching or standing invisibly, pulls out two puppets at a time from a pocket sewn into his tent. With the movement of the fingers on which the puppets are placed, the puppets become "souled". "Chadir Jamal" appeared in the territory of Uzbekistan approximately in the 5th century. It developed widely in the XIV-XVI centuries. It mainly reflected events taken from real life.

Tent dream is a type of traditional Uzbek puppet art. Usually, the head, chin, chest, elbows, wrists, knees, ankles of the puppets are tied with threads, and one end is connected to the handle moves them by pulling. Back in the park, street or yard a place with a natural beam is chosen, and so on. 5-6 m long, 2-2.5 m long colored or striped curtain. It will be cut in the middle. Behind this place, which is called the tent, there is an inner black tent with a length of 3-3.5 meters and a height of 20-25 cm. The lower side of it is also cut to a length of 180 cm and a height of 70-75 cm, and a playing area is formed. The interior of the tent is supported by a device consisting of a threshold, a column, a beam, and supports. Half there will be a black back curtain inside up to a meter.

Performances are usually shown in the evening and 50 puppets are played. "Chadir Hayal" is approx VI appeared in the centuries. XIV developed widely from the 2nd half of the century to the beginning of the 16th century. Initially, folk legends and mythological plots were covered, XVIII-XIX in centuries, it depicted palace life and market scenes with satirical colors. The types of puppet plays of the folk performance art, their historical trends, famous performers and repertoires of history are perfectly covered by Mukhsin Kadirov, Doctor of Art Sciences, in his books "Puppet Theater" and "Uzbek Folk Performance Art".

In our country, writes Mukhsin Kadyrov, "puppet play", in particular, the types of puppetry, which are played on the hand, controlled by a string and shadowed, were widespread in the past. They were called "Chadir Jamal", "Chadir Imagination" and "Fonus Imagination". Compared to "Chadir Jamal", the performances of "Chadir Khayam" were more complex and perfect.

Theater performances were usually shown in the evenings, and due to the use of noise and noise, the strings of the puppets inside the black curtains were not visible, creating a natural and strange scene as if the puppets themselves were moving. Each skilled puppeteer was able to move 8-10 puppets at the same time with the help of strings. At the "Hand Puppet" theater, a maximum of ten puppets took part in one performance, while at "Chadir Khayam" more than fifty puppets played at once. In these theaters, music served as an artistic decoration, more as a means of expressing the state of the characters. The puppeteers-

composers created a number of wonderful tunes specially for puppet games, such as "Ufor", "Miyankhana", "Charkh", "Duchava Parron", "Chogollaq", "Ot Eraniy", "Kum Pishighi", "Torgai Chirillama".

In Central Asia, this type of folk performances, such as "Chadir Jamal", "Chadir Imagination", "Fonus Imagination" for many years, even the Arabs (VII-VIII centuries,) then the Mongols (XIII century) did not stop its activity during the occupation period or after it. It only partly changed its form, adapting to the new conditions of social life and the requirements of Islam. If we look at the history, the art of puppetry in our country has a history of twenty centuries. In the territory of Uzbekistan, types of puppetry have developed in connection with rituals.

In Europe, first in Italy XVI century, and in Russia XVIII-XIX century this art is recorded. It can be seen that the peoples of Central Asia achieved progress in the development of puppetry art compared to European countries and Russia several centuries ago. The group of puppeteers traveled from village to village on the dusty roads of Central Asia, neither hot nor cold, sometimes in carts, sometimes on foot, and performed in caravansary, crowded markets, squares. There is a scene in Abdullah Qadiri's novel "Otkan Kunlar" where the puppeteers mock the khans. Based on the requirements of the ideology of that time, the show tells about the ugly life of Kokand Khan Khudoyorkhan, palace vices. They laughed at the flaws existing in the society of that time, bravely defended the deceived and humiliated people.

Doctor of Art Studies, Professor Muhsin Kadyrov IX-XII century turns to the work of Umar Khayyam, a prominent thinker of Central Asia, in studying the art of puppetry. Omar Khayyam

It is said in the rubai:

"We are puppets, the sky is a puppeteer,

This is a true word, not a metaphor.

We will fall one by one into the chest of absence,

A little while playing on the plane of existence" [2, B. 10].

Based on allusions and metaphors in the artistic language reflected in Rubaiyyah, the scientist draws certain scientific conclusions about the art of puppetry in the countries where the poet lived, studied, and visited as a tourist, i.e., Iran, Khorasan, and Movarounnahr. It can be seen that the art of puppetry was active even during the time of Omar Khayyam. In particular, they tried to reveal some of the country's ills through this art form.

Collecting information about the culture and art of the past, researching them based on various sources, leads to a deeper knowledge of the art of puppetry. We can also learn from Pahlavon Mahmud's rubai that there was a sharp revival in the art of puppetry in the 13th-14th centuries. The Rubaiyat explains that it comes from historical sources about the countries the poet traveled to with the following lines:

"We wonder in the universe,
Fonus is an example and we are wandering.
If the sun is a lamp, the world is a lantern,
Like dolls in the night we wander" [3, B. 16].

Based on the above Rubaiyats, it can be said that Umar Khayyam and Pahlavon Mahmud tried to reveal the social conditions of their time through "Chadir Imagination" and "Fonus Imagination" in a metaphorical sense. XV-XVI The work of the great poet Alisher Navoi also serves as an important source in studying the state of the art of puppetry in the centuries. The great poet expresses his thoughts about puppetry in his poem "Hayratul Abror".

In conclusion, it should be noted that the art of puppetry is considered to be of great importance in folk games. In "Chadir Jamal" where puppets are played with hands, life events are depicted, in "Chadir Imagination" which is controlled by strings, mythology is reflected in "Fonus Imagination" which casts a shadow. Puppeteers clearly expressed their relationship with the ruling class through this art.

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